

THE PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO
THE STUDY OF THE TRIAD N·C·S. PART VIII.
THE CHEMISTRY OF HECTOR'S BASE AND
ATTEMPTS TOWARDS ITS SYNTHESIS.

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Hector's base, $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$ (I) is formed very readily on oxidation of phenylthiocarbamide (II) in presence of a little acid and may be expected to throw light on the constitution of (II). Contrary to Fromm's supposition (*Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 3804) (I) appears to be a direct oxidation product of (II). This view is suggested by the negative results obtained by oxidising together, (i) (II) and phenylcyanamide, (ii) monophenylguanidine and phenylmustard oil and, (iii) diphenylguanidine and thiocvanic acid respectively. The above theory has been further supported by the reaction between nitrous acid and (II) studied in presence of relatively concentrated acid.

Hector (*Ber.*, 1889, **22**, 1176) obtained a base ($C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$) on oxidising phenylthiocarbamide with hydrogen peroxide in presence of a little acid. Subsequent workers obtained it with other oxidising agents, e.g., bromine in alcoholic solution (Hugershoff, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 3130), nitrous acid (Haager and Doht, *Monatsh.*, 1906, **27**, 267), *p*-toluenesulphuryl chloride (Fromm and Heyder, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 3804), and catalytic oxidation with air (Fruendlich and Bjerke, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1916, **9**, 1). The chemistry of the base does not seem to be well known. It is, however, astonishing to find that copper sulphate, a reagent less known for its oxidising properties, yields the base from phenylthiocarbamide (*cf.* Lal and Krall, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **8**, 477), whilst silver nitrate fails to do so.

Hector originally represented the base by the structure (I) and named it dianilino-*o*-diazothioliol or diphenyldiamido-*o*-diazothioliol according to Widman's nomenclature (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1892, *ii*, **48**, 200), but later considered it to possess structure (II) of an azosulphime type probably on the suggestion of Hofmann and Gabriel (*Ber.*, 1892, **25**, 1578). Dost (*Ber.*, 1906, **39**, 863) on hydrolysing the base with fuming hydrochloric acid found that only one :NH group could be split off, the hydrolytic product being a non-basic keto compound.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

He, therefore, favoured structure (III) which contains only one imino group, though the possibility of structure (IV) is not thus precluded.

With regard to the mechanism of its formation, Fromm (*loc. cit.*) like other workers supposed that the first product of oxidation of phenylthiocarbamide was actually a disulphide (A) in analogy with the case of thiocarbamide (*cf.* Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2180), thus :

The compound (A) was then considered to decompose into sulphur, phenylthiocarbamide, and phenylcyanamide, from which the diazthiol was ultimately built up. From this theory it occurred to the present authors that it should be possible to get Hector's base from suitable residues of compounds (*vide infra*) if the base represents a stable configuration built up of simpler molecules. The present communication records the results of such attempts and suggests that the base is a direct oxidation product of phenylthiocarbamide. This is further supported by the action of nitrous acid on phenylthiocarbamide (Mehta and Krall, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 635).

According to Fromm (*loc. cit.*) phenylthiocarbamide and phenylcyanamide, when oxidised together, should yield Hector's base. When, however, these two compounds in alcoholic solution are oxidised in presence of a little acid with hydrogen peroxide (*vide experimental*), sulphur separates and the yield of the base is not greater than that obtainable without the cyanamide. Monophenylguanidine and phenylmustard oil give a non-basic compound (m.p. 198°) which does not produce Hector's base on oxidation. The possibility of the alternative structure (IV) was tested by reacting diphenylguanidine with thiocyanic acid, the product being diphenylguanidine thiocyanate, which on oxidation did not give Hector's base. The amounts of the separated sulphur and of Hector's base in the action of sodium nitrite

on phenylthiocarbamide (*cf.* Mehta and Krall, *loc. cit.*) correspond to the direct oxidation of about half of the thiocarbamide according to the following equation

From this fact it appears that Hector's base is not a secondary product as supposed by Fromm.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Oxidation of Phenylcyanamide and Phenylthiocarbamide.—Moist phenylcyanamide (2.5 g.) was added to a solution of phenylthiocarbamide (2.5 g.) in alcohol (70 c.c.). The solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid (1 c.c.). A 3% solution of hydrogen peroxide (10-12 g.) was gradually added when sulphur separated. The mixture was diluted to about 150 c.c. with water and filtered from separated sulphur (0.2 g.). The filtrate, which was slightly cloudy (phenylcyanamide), was basified with alkali which precipitated Hector's base (1.8 g.; theoretical yield without using the cyanamide being 2.1 g.). The phenylcyanamide appeared to remain unchanged. The result was identical when dilute alcoholic solutions were employed.

Oxidation of Monophenylguanidine and Phenylmustard Oil.—The guanidine was prepared (*a*) from cyanamide and aniline hydrochloride (Kampf, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 1681) and also (*b*) by a method based on that of Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 1790). The melt was extracted with water and the aqueous extract basified with alkali. In each case monophenylguanidine was isolated from basified solution as carbonate (m.p. 138°) by precipitation with a solution of saturated potassium carbonate, identified through its benzoyl derivative (m.p. 186°). An alcoholic suspension of phenylguanidine carbonate (1.66 g.) was neutralised with acetic acid and mixed with an alcoholic solution of phenylmustard oil (1.35 g.). After warming for 14 minutes the mixture was treated with 3% hydrogen peroxide (6.8 g.). When placed overnight it gave needle-shaped crystals of a non-basic compound m.p. 198°, containing S and N, which was not Hector's base. The compound gave an acetyl derivative (m. p. 235°) and could also be obtained from the above constituents without the addition of hydrogen peroxide.

Oxidation of Diphenylguanidine and Thiocyanic Acid.—Equivalent quantities of diphenylguanidine and thiocyanic acid in ethereal solution were mixed when diphenylguanidine thiocyanate (m. p. 115°) was obtained. This did not give Hector's base on oxidation with hydrogen peroxide and remained unchanged on heating.

Action of Nitrous Acid on Phenylthiocarbamide dissolved in concentrated Hydrochloric Acid.—Phenylthiocarbamide (3.04 g.) was dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (16 c.c.) in a separating funnel. The solution was treated slowly with aqueous sodium nitrite (20 c. c. M.), and the contents of the separating funnel were cooled by running water (18-19°). The reaction began with brisk evolution of gas and the solution smelt of isocyanide and of phenylmustard oil. The small amount of the oily and resinous mass was removed by extraction with 5 c. c. of chloroform thrice. The aqueous layer remained clear for 2 hours and deposited sulphur (0.2 g; theoretical 0.32 g.) on dilution and slight warming. The filtrate from it contained sulphuric acid (3.4%), Hector's base (1.05 g, identified through its nitroso derivative and the acetyl derivative) and unchanged thiocarbamide.

In conclusion it might be mentioned that Barnett (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 63) only obtained an oil on oxidising phenylthiocarbamide in the absence of an acid and not Hector's base. With thiocarbamide under this condition, the product according to him was a derivative of sulphinic acid which has been further investigated by Boesken (*Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1936, 39, 717; *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1936, 55, 1040, 1044). Oxidation reactions of the thiocarbamides are proposed to be further investigated.

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